

Reactions of Copper(II) Salts with Benzoylacetone and γ -Picoline or Imidazole

C. M. DANI

Research and Control Laboratory, Rourkela Steel Plant, Rourkela-769 011
and

A. K. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, Government College, Rourkela-769 004

Manuscript received 2 February 1984, accepted 6 February 1986

Six mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{bzac})\text{L}_2\text{X}]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{bzac})\text{L}_2\text{ClO}_4]$, where bzacH = benzoyl acetone, L = γ -picoline or imidazole and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$ or NO_3^- have been synthesised by reacting the cupric salts with benzoylacetone and γ -picoline or imidazole in 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio in ethanol medium. The analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral data reveal that the complexes of the first and second categories are square-planar and pentacoordinated, respectively.

THERE has been considerable interest in recent years, in the study of mixed ligand complexes of metal β -diketonates with ligands containing different donor atoms of varying electronegativities, in view of their significance and diverse uses. Some mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) containing dibenzoylmethane and nitrogen donor ligands have been reported¹ in an earlier communication. In continuation of our studies² on mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} containing acetylacetonate, trichloroacetate and N, S or O donors, we report in the present communication, the results of the reactions of Cu^{2+} salts with benzoylacetone and γ -picoline or imidazole in 1 : 1 : 2 stoichiometric ratio in ethanol medium.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH AnalaR quality.

Preparation of complexes : The complexes were prepared by refluxing ethanolic solutions of Cu^{2+} salts, benzoylacetone and γ -picoline or imidazole in 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio for about 30 min and then keeping the resulting solutions overnight. The complexes were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol several times followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Analyses and physical measurements : Analyses of copper and chloride were carried out by standard methods. Carbon and hydrogen were determined microanalytically. Magnetic measurements of the complexes were conducted at room temperature by Gouy method. Molar conductances of the complexes in DMF were measured using a Systronic

303 direct reading conductivity meter. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} and electronic spectra of the complexes in chloroform medium were recorded using Hitachi 320 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data and some of the physicochemical properties of the complexes (Table 1) are consistent with the proposed formulations. The room temperature magnetic moment values of 1.84-1.97 B.M. suggest the paramagnetic nature of the Cu^{2+} complexes containing one unpaired electron. The complexes are fairly soluble in methanol, chloroform and dimethylformamide. Chloride and nitrate complexes have Λ_M values in the range, 43.2-51.7 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ suggesting 1 : 1 electrolytic nature of the complexes. The molar conductance values 6.2-7.0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ of the perchlorate complexes indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

Ir spectra : Some important ir bands of diagnostic importance are discussed. In the present complexes, the occurrence of bands due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ around 1610-1582 and 1545-1540 cm^{-1} , respectively reveals^{3,4} the presence of coordinated β -diketone group of benzoylacetone. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ bands of γ -picoline observed at 1610, 1570 and 1498 cm^{-1} are shifted to 1615, 1552 and 1508 cm^{-1} , respectively in the γ -picoline complexes indicating⁴⁻⁶ coordination of the ligand through the nitrogen atom. The absorption band centering at 3165 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of imidazole is attributed to $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{H}}$ and is shifted 10-15 cm^{-1} to

* Present address : Bonaigarh College, Bonaigarh, Dt. Sundargarh, Orissa.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II)

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				$\Delta\nu$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Cu	Cl	C	H		
[Cu(bzac)(γ -pic) ₂]Cl	Shining green	155.0	14.28 (14.24)	7.14 (7.95)	59.6 (59.19)	4.98 (5.15)	50.4	1.84
[Cu(bzac)(Iz) ₂]Cl	Light blue	182.0	15.95 (16.03)	8.48 (8.95)	48.26 (48.46)	4.01 (4.29)	46.8	1.89
[Cu(bzac)(γ -pic) ₂]NO ₃	Green	172.0	13.91 (13.44)		55.21 (55.86)	5.11 (4.86)	51.7	1.92
[Cu(bzac)(Iz) ₂]NO ₃	Green	190.0	14.48 (15.03)		44.94 (45.42)	3.89 (4.02)	43.2	1.97
[Cu(bzac)(γ -pic) ₂]ClO ₄]	Shining green	132.0	12.10 (12.45)		50.96 (51.76)	4.21 (4.50)	6.2	1.85
[Cu(bzac)(Iz) ₂]ClO ₄]	Shining green	188.0	14.40 (13.80)		41.10 (41.72)	3.10 (3.69)	7.0	1.84

lower frequencies in the imidazole complexes. A shift in ν_{C-N} from 1582 to $\sim$ 1560 cm^{-1} and the presence of ν_{N-H} in the spectra of these complexes suggest the involvement of tertiary nitrogen of imidazole in coordination. The nitrate complexes, [Cu(bzac)L₂]NO₃ show a strong N—O stretching mode around 1350 cm^{-1} (ν_3) region and two ir active deformation modes around 850 (ν_2) and 760 cm^{-1} (ν_4). These indicate ionic nature of the nitrate ion having D_{3h} symmetry⁸⁻¹⁰. The perchlorate complexes display three sharp bands at $\sim$ 1100, $\sim$ 1080 and $\sim$ 1070 cm^{-1} , and another band at $\sim$ 920 cm^{-1} suggesting the coordinated behaviour of ClO₄⁻ ion¹¹⁻¹⁴. Further, monodentate behaviour of ClO₄⁻ is supported by the absence of ν_{Cl-O_2} band around 1270-1245 cm^{-1} . The non-ligand bands occurring around 428-418 cm^{-1} and 322-300 cm^{-1} regions may tentatively be assigned to ν_{Cu-O} and ν_{Cu-N} modes, respectively.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of chloride and nitrate complexes show two absorption bands at $\sim$ 540 and 660 nm which may be assigned to $^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ and $^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3B_{2g}$ transitions, respectively for a square-planar stereochemistry^{15,16} around copper(II). The observed spectra further eliminate¹⁷ the possibility of tetrahedral or pseudo-tetrahedral structure for the complexes. The presence of a broad electronic spectral band at $\sim$ 640 nm in the perchlorate complexes, favours pentacoordination around copper(II)¹⁸⁻²⁰. However, X-ray studies alone can reveal the exact stereochemistry of these pentacoordinated complexes.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Prof. D. V. Ramana Rao, for encouragement, the management of Rourkela Steel Plant, for providing facilities, and

the R.S.I.C. at C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for running the spectra of the complexes.

References

1. K. M. PUROHIT and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 437.
2. C. M. DANI and A. K. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 381.
3. S. N. DAS and K. C. DASH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 459.
4. R. C. PAUL and S. L. CHADHA, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1966, 22, 615.
5. R. C. PAUL and S. L. CHADHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 272.
6. D. FORSTER and D. M. L. GOODGAME, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2790.
7. A. K. DAS and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 481.
8. N. F. CURTIS and Y. M. CURTIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 804.
9. C. C. ADDISON and D. F. SUTTON, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 8, 1169.
10. B. M. GATEHOUSE, S. E. LIVINGSTONE and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4227.
11. L. E. MOORE, R. B. GAYHERT and W. E. BULL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, 24, 898.
12. K. NAKAMATO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1970, p. 175.
13. G. DYER, J. G. HARTLEY and L. M. VENANZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 3091.
14. I. M. PROCTOR, B. J. HATHAWAY and P. J. NICHOLLS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 1678.
15. L. SACCONI and M. J. CIAMPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 276.
16. J. BJERRUM, C. J. BALHAUSEN and C. K. JOGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, 8, 1275.
17. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 359.
18. T. SHIGEMATSU, M. TABUSHI, M. MATSUI and M. MUNAKATA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1968, 41, 2656.
19. P. E. RAKITA, S. KOPPERL and J. P. PACKLER, JR. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 2139.
20. R. D. GILLARD and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1963, 359.